

Basic Disaster Skills During and After Disaster According to the Opinions of Firefighters

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Abstract

This qualitative research was conducted with 19 experienced firefighters from the İzmir Metropolitan Municipality Fire Department, aiming to identify the essential skills citizens need during and after disasters. The study includes in-depth insights and experiences of the participants. According to the research results, primary skills highlighted during disasters include remaining calm, communication proficiency, moving to safe zones, trusting and collaborating with experts, and minimizing damage. Secondary skills emphasize practical abilities such as going to assembly points, reaching high places, possessing first aid knowledge, effective communication and information sharing, and preventing hazardous situations. The research indicates that citizens are expected to focus on primary skills like assisting search and rescue teams, going to assembly points, maintaining healthy communication and coordination, staying calm and hopeful, and collaborating with search and rescue teams during and after disasters. Secondary skills such as first aid, hygiene, personal care, social and psychological support aim to protect citizens' health, provide emotional support, and strengthen community solidarity after disasters. This research contributes significantly to promoting active citizen participation in disaster management and the development of curricula and policies based on disaster literacy skills.

Keywords: *Disaster literacy skills, firefighters' perspective, citizen education.*

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Introduction

Disasters pose an increasing global concern, significantly impacting communities and individuals. This impact is influenced by a myriad of factors such as climate change, geographical elements, and human-induced factors, amplifying the frequency and severity of disasters (Becken et al., 2014; Rosselló et al., 2020). In conjunction with sustainable development and global environmental changes, the relationship between natural events and humans has become increasingly important for communities to be prepared for disasters and embrace sustainability principles (Smith, 2013). In this context, the presence of citizens capable of responding to disasters in a prepared and educated manner is of paramount importance (Joseph et al., 2020; Karacaoğlu, 2023; Varol, 2019). Literacy and education on disasters for citizens play a critical role in aiding individuals and communities in being prepared for disasters. The identification of fundamental skills in disaster literacy is a crucial step in this educational process. According to the definition by Brown et al. (2014), disaster literacy is the ability of an individual to make informed decisions, intervene, and follow instructions during rescue processes in disaster situations. These fundamental skills will assist communities exposed to disasters in being effectively prepared and acting efficiently in the face of events.

Challenges in Disaster Response

The willingness demonstrated in responding to disasters highlights repeated problems such as weak integration of intervention activities and inadequate training of managers (Khorram-Manesh et al., 2016).

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This underscores the necessity for a new approach to disaster management. Research indicates that emergency training is not only required for professionals but also for citizens (Bodas et al., 2019; Helsloot & Ruitenberg, 2004; Karacaoğlu, 2024; Peleg et al., 2018). Karacaoğlu et al.'s (2024) research emphasizes that many individuals providing support during earthquakes lack training and sufficient knowledge. Bodas and others (2019) suggest that professional teams may be insufficient in the first 24-48 hours and may not reach all victims. Aydemir (2021) underscores the importance of active community participation for a qualified disaster management system. Active community participation enables citizens to enhance their capacities for preparedness and effective communication with others. Therefore, imparting basic skills of first aid and search and rescue to citizens is essential for widespread adoption across communities.

Education and Future Preparedness

One of the primary functions of education is to prepare future workers and citizens to cope with challenges they may face. This is achievable through knowledge and skill development, providing the kind of preparation that will be needed in the future (Trilling & Fadel, 2009). Today, education has become crucial for success in economic life and living in prosperity. However, there is a clear need for adaptation to the changing education needs of our time. Rapid technological advancements, globalization, and the requirements of working life necessitate making education compatible. Learning experiences today require not only understanding complex academic content but also applying knowledge to new problems and situations (Wagner, 2008). Perhaps we have transitioned from the information age to the "skill age." However, scholars struggle to define basic skills as there is no consensus in the literature regarding citizenship skills (Lai & Veiring, 2012). In this context, Karacaoğlu (2022) has listed 18 essential skills that individuals need in the 21st century. These skills include creativity, communication, problem-solving, critical thinking, empathy, entrepreneurship, innovation, collaboration, and professionalism. Using this method and approach to identify these basic skills, this research aims to determine the fundamental disaster literacy skills that every global citizen should possess. These skills, crucial for search and rescue personnel in the fire department, will be addressed to support effective intervention processes during and after disasters. In the existing literature, there is a limited number of studies on disaster literacy and these skills from the perspective of fire search and rescue personnel (Abelsson, 2019; Elkady et al., 2022; Nunavath et al., 2016; Sommer & Njå, 2011). This research aims to fill these knowledge gaps and contribute to a better understanding of basic disaster literacy skills in the context of the views of fire search and rescue personnel.

Focus on Firefighters' Perspectives

According to the data put forward by Ütük and Baraçlı (2024), who suggest that fire brigade organizations should assume a pioneering role in disaster response, fire brigade urban search and rescue units are formed in settlements with a population of more than 50,000. Light search and rescue teams are formed in settlements with a population between 50,000-100,000, medium in settlements between 100,000-300,000 and heavy in settlements with a population of more than 300,000. In addition, in settlements with a population exceeding 3,000,000, one heavy search and rescue team must be established for every 3,000,000 people.

The significance of firefighters' services has notably increased due to urbanization, establishing them as pivotal first responders in disasters. Through close collaboration with local communities, firefighters strive to mitigate the negative impacts of fires, disasters, and emergencies (Demirci & Özçelik, 2021; Hirsch, 2013; Nyimbili & Erden, 2020; Şahan, 2021). The necessity of focusing on the views of firefighters involved in disaster response is evident. This preference stems from the psychologically challenging situations that firefighters, in their professional roles and uniforms, encounter. Firefighters bear critical responsibilities, including preserving the dignity of the injured or deceased, shielding colleagues from the effects of accident tragedies, and ensuring general safety. Additionally, possessing robust medical training to effectively intervene in emergencies is a vital requirement for firefighting personnel (Abelsson, 2019). Professional teams expected to provide initial intervention in any type of disaster are often comprised of firefighters. This research, by identifying disaster literacy skills through the perspectives of firefighters, particularly those with expertise in search and rescue, can contribute to

an increased appreciation for and understanding of the significance of firefighters' contributions to the lives and well-being of others.

Importance of Information and Education

Keçici and Bıçakçı (2023) identified the lack of information and education as primary factors influencing the magnitude of disasters. Evaluating the impacts of 380 disasters in Turkey between 1923 and 2023 using data from the International Disaster Database (EM-DAT, 2023), the researchers found that these events resulted in the loss of 142,614 lives, affecting 19,462,768 individuals, with an estimated total damage of 86,950,981,000 US dollars. These statistics hold significant importance in enhancing disaster coping capabilities, minimizing casualties and damages, promoting disaster awareness within society, and ensuring the resilience of individuals through education. Consequently, the research focuses on the fundamental skills that every citizen should possess during and after disasters. By consulting experienced firefighters, particularly those with expertise in search and rescue, the study aims to identify the essential skills needed by communities in disaster situations. This research seeks to provide a more detailed understanding of disaster literacy skills from the perspective of firefighters and offer valuable insights into the critical nature of these skills across society.

Methods

In this research, a qualitative research approach has been adopted based on the perspectives of 19 firefighters who have participated in numerous search and rescue operations. The aim is to identify the essential skills that every citizen should possess during and after disasters by leveraging the experiences and viewpoints of firefighters. The qualitative research approach provides an opportunity for participants to share in-depth insights and experiences, allowing researchers to gain a deeper and richer understanding of the subject.

Participants

The study group consists of 19 firefighters serving in the Izmir Metropolitan Municipality Fire Department, who have expertise in search and rescue and form the focal point of the research.

Data Collection

A storage technique developed by Karacaoğlu and Bayrakçı (2020) was used for data collection. The purpose of this technique is to facilitate participant interaction without being influenced by each other's views and to share their accumulated knowledge. A glass jar and six different colored papers were used for the application. The steps were as follows:

1. Participants were informed about the purpose and application steps of the technique.
2. Each participant was given one piece of paper in six different colors.
3. Participants were asked to write the most important information related to the topic.
4. After completing the writing process, participants folded the papers and placed them inside the glass jar, remembering what they wrote on each colored paper.
5. Each participant then picked another colored paper from the jar.
6. Reading what was written on the paper silently, participants wrote the third piece of important information and folded the paper again.
7. In the evaluation stage, all papers were sequentially taken out, read aloud for group discussion, each item was discussed and categorized individually. Opinions were evaluated, written, and frequencies were extracted. This process brought together the information stored in the glass jar to create a common list.

As a result, all the information accumulated in the glass jar was compiled to create the group's collective product. The 19 participants in the study group expressed the necessary skills during and after disasters in two rounds. A total of 95 distinct perspectives were collated, comprising 45 insights related to skills required during disasters and 50 pertaining to those necessary after disasters.

Data Analysis

In the data analysis phase, content analysis was used to examine the information collected through the storage technique. The dataset underwent a thorough examination to identify fundamental concepts, expressions, and patterns, each of which was then assigned a specific code. These codes were subsequently grouped to form overarching themes, allowing us to bring together similar or interconnected codes and pinpoint the central themes emerging from the data. To enhance clarity and coherence, the identified codes and themes underwent a process of organization, resulting in the creation of a meaningful and systematic structure. This systematic arrangement played a crucial role in rendering the data more comprehensible. As a culmination of this organized framework of themes and codes, we derived findings that align with the objectives of our research. This comprehensive approach to content analysis contributed to a nuanced understanding of the data and facilitated the extraction of meaningful insights. The data analysis process is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Data Analysis Process Flowchart

This schematic breakdown outlines the sequential stages involved in the data analysis process, from coding and theme extraction to the organization of codes and themes, ultimately leading to the derivation of findings aligned with the research objective. After recording the data obtained using the storage technique, the classification process was initiated, and information was organized for a clearer presentation. This organization ensured that the data became more meaningful and understandable. During the analysis process, the descriptive analysis method was used, providing a detailed explanation of the obtained data for better understanding (Punch, 2013). The storage technique offered the advantage of being open to participant evaluations during the analysis stage. Skill expressions were organized, merged, and themes were created according to participant views. Data were classified through common decisions among participants. As a result, 10 fundamental skills during disasters and 18 fundamental skills

after disasters were identified. The data revealed skills prioritized by at least three participants as primary skills, while others were analyzed as secondary skills.

Findings

The research conducted on disaster management and citizen preparedness has unearthed valuable insights into the critical aspects of emergency response and community resilience. Through an in-depth analysis of firefighter perspectives, the study underscores the importance of enhancing citizens' skills before and during disasters.

Essential Skills During Disasters

According to the perspectives of firefighters, 10 primary citizenship skills required during disasters have been identified. Skills with a frequency of 3 or more are categorized as primary, while others are considered secondary skills and presented in tabular form. Frequencies have been interpreted based on participants expressing the same skills without being aware of each other. The findings related to primary citizenship skills required during disasters are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Primary Citizenship Skills Required During Disasters

Primary Skills	Frequency
Remaining calm and composed	14
Clear communication with provided information	12
Moving from enclosed space to a safe area	4
Assisting search and rescue teams, trusting, prioritizing	4
Attempting to improve conditions to minimize damage (e.g., Life Triangle)	3

Table 1, based on the views of firefighters, provides essential insights into the primary skills prioritized during disasters. Participants particularly emphasized the skill of remaining calm during disasters, representing an individual's ability to control thoughts and actions without succumbing to panic. This quality stands out as a fundamental skill for effective disaster coping. Clear and accurate communication holds critical importance during disasters. Participants highlighted the significance of equipping individuals and communities with up-to-date and accurate information. Firefighters emphasized that effective communication is a key element in the disaster management process.

The strategy of evacuating from hazardous areas is vital during disaster situations. Firefighters emphasized the importance of individuals moving to safe areas and identified this skill as a fundamental strategy for minimizing the consequences of disasters. Additionally, participants underscored the importance of trusting and collaborating with search and rescue experts during disasters. This skill entails accepting professional assistance from the community and coordinating it effectively. Participants also emphasized strategies for minimizing damage. This skill involves individuals understanding and improving the conditions in their surroundings.

In conclusion, Table 1 provides an overview of the primary skills prioritized by firefighters during disasters. These skills encompass individuals ensuring their safety, aiding their communities, and effectively utilizing professional assistance.

Secondary Citizenship Skills During Disasters

The findings related to secondary citizenship skills required during disasters are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Secondary Citizenship Skills Required During Disasters

Secondary Skills	Frequency
Going to assembly points	2
Climbing to a high place (for flood disasters)	2
First aid knowledge	2
Calling, waking, informing people in the vicinity	1
Shutting off the gas line	1

Table 2 provides the frequencies of secondary citizenship skills based on the views of firefighters. These skills include practical measures specific to disaster situations but are more specific and limited compared to primary skills. The skill of going to designated assembly points aims to facilitate organized gathering of the community and transitioning to a safe area. This skill ensures effective guidance of individuals towards assembly and assistance points post-disaster.

The ability to climb to a high point during situations like floods targets protection against water inundation. This skill is crucial for directing individuals to safe areas in the face of risky conditions. Firefighters emphasized the importance of basic first aid knowledge during disasters. First aid aims to improve emergency interventions and the condition of the injured. This skill focuses on effectively intervening in injuries that may occur during disasters and saving lives.

The skill of calling, waking, and informing people in the vicinity represents the ability of individuals to assist others in their environment and communicate information. This skill strengthens communication among individuals in the community, supporting a culture of mutual assistance and solidarity. The skill of shutting off the gas line is aimed at preventing dangerous situations like gas leaks during disasters. This skill encourages a conscious and proactive response to environmental hazards. Table 2 illustrates in detail the secondary skills prioritized by firefighters during disasters. These skills represent the capacity to respond to more specialized and specific needs related to disaster situations.

Essential Skills After Disasters

According to firefighter perspectives, 18 primary citizenship skills required after disasters have been identified. Skills with a frequency of 3 or more are categorized as primary, while others are considered secondary skills and presented in tabular form. Frequencies have been interpreted based on participants expressing the same skills without being aware of each other. The findings related to primary citizenship skills required after disasters are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Primary Citizenship Skills Required After Disasters

Primary Skills	Frequency
Assisting search and rescue teams	10
Going to assembly and waiting areas	9
Establishing healthy communication and coordination	7
Remaining calm and hopeful	5
Collaborating with search and rescue teams	3

Table 3 illustrates the frequencies of primary citizenship skills expected from individuals after disasters based on firefighter perspectives. Firefighters have prioritized the skill of assisting search and rescue teams as primary. This skill involves providing support to professional teams and identifying those in need of assistance during emergencies. The skill of going to designated assembly areas and waiting there is aimed at establishing a safe and organized post-disaster setup. This skill prevents individuals from moving uncontrollably and allows for more effective coordination of aid.

Firefighters also emphasize the importance of healthy communication and coordination skills post-disaster. This skill involves effective communication among disaster survivors and professional rescue

teams. Individuals are expected to remain calm and hopeful after disasters, representing emotional resilience and a positive attitude during crisis situations. Collaborating with search and rescue teams is another primary skill expected from individuals after disasters. This skill involves coordinated actions and mutual assistance with professional teams. Table 3 clearly presents the perspective of firefighters on the primary skills expected from individuals after disasters.

Secondary Citizenship Skills After Disasters

The findings related to secondary citizenship skills required after disasters are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Secondary Citizenship Skills Required After Disasters

Secondary Skills	Frequency
First aid	2
Hygiene and personal care	2
Social and psychological support	2
Correct and effective use of social media	1
Providing accurate information to authorities	1
Being cautious during rescue operations (for earthquake disasters)	1
Supporting other disaster survivors	1
Remaining silent during search and rescue operations (for earthquake disasters)	1
Creating social security measures	1
Ability to set up a toilet tent	1
Adhering to guidelines and instructions from authorities and experts	1
Applying theoretical knowledge learned in training	1
Assisting with transportation	1
First aid	1

Table 4 highlights various priorities among secondary citizenship skills expected from individuals after disasters, based on firefighter perspectives. The skill of first aid has been emphasized by two participants, representing the ability to intervene in health issues that may arise post-disaster. This underscores the importance placed on addressing injuries or emergency situations at the scene. Hygiene and personal care skills have also been mentioned by two participants. This skill involves measures to maintain health conditions, cleanliness, and personal hygiene after a disaster. Social and psychological support is another skill emphasized by two participants. This skill focuses on providing emotional support to disaster survivors and encouraging solidarity within the community.

Other secondary skills have been mentioned by only one participant each. These skills include the correct and effective use of social media, providing accurate information to authorities, being cautious during rescue operations (for earthquake disasters), supporting other disaster survivors, remaining silent during search and rescue operations (for earthquake disasters), creating social security measures, the ability to set up a toilet tent, adhering to guidelines and instructions from authorities and experts, applying theoretical knowledge learned in training, and assisting with transportation. Table 4 reveals that firefighters expect a broad spectrum of secondary skills from individuals after disasters, addressing various needs within the community.

The presented findings offer a comprehensive understanding of the essential citizenship skills identified by firefighters during and after disasters. The primary skills emphasized during disasters include remaining calm, clear communication, moving to safe areas, assisting search and rescue teams, and improving conditions to minimize damage. After disasters, primary skills focus on assisting search and rescue teams, going to assembly areas, establishing healthy communication, remaining calm and hopeful, and collaborating with search and rescue teams.

Secondary skills during disasters encompass going to assembly points, climbing to high places (for flood disasters), first aid knowledge, calling, waking, and informing people in the vicinity, and shutting off the gas line. After disasters, secondary skills include first aid, hygiene and personal care, social and

psychological support, correct and effective use of social media, providing accurate information to authorities, being cautious during rescue operations (for earthquake disasters), supporting other disaster survivors, remaining silent during search and rescue operations (for earthquake disasters), creating social security measures, the ability to set up a toilet tent, adhering to guidelines and instructions from authorities and experts, applying theoretical knowledge learned in training, and assisting with transportation.

These findings can serve as a valuable guide for developing educational programs, community awareness initiatives, and disaster preparedness strategies aimed at equipping individuals with the necessary skills to navigate and recover from disasters effectively.

Results and Discussion

The results of the study highlight the diversity of primary and secondary essential skills required during disasters from the perspective of firefighters, based on data obtained. According to Helsloot and Ruitenbergh (2004), it has been stated that citizens are generally the most effective emergency personnel. Disaster assessments show that most lives are actually saved by "average" citizens. Research by Reynolds et al. (2002) indicates that the community is often the group that best responds to risk avoidance and damage reduction education after a disaster. Therefore, imparting basic disaster literacy skills to citizens during and after disasters, especially in disaster-prone countries, is of paramount importance.

According to experienced firefighters, the two most critical skills that citizens should possess during disasters are remaining calm and composed and effective communication. The efforts of governments during the COVID-19 pandemic to reassure their citizens with the phrase "new normal" are supportive of these findings. This policy, while potentially endangering public health, is a narrative aimed at creating calmness (Alnizar & Manshur, 2022). The two fundamental skills required during a disaster, "remaining calm and composed," are directly related to each other; citizens who are "calm and composed" can engage in more constructive "communication" (Holmström et al., 2022). Hansson et al. (2020) and Eyüboğlu and Kodak (2023) emphasize that individuals exposed to disasters can become vulnerable when they lack access to information sources and other people or have limited access. In a disaster situation, the effective and rapid dissemination of disaster information is critical for reducing casualties and damage (Chiimba & Verne, 2022). These findings demonstrate how crucial the lack of reliable communication channels is during moments of disaster. Access to reliable, continuous, and clear information should be provided to the community in such challenging situations. Relying on scientists and scientific data is an important factor for trust among participants. Fallou et al. (2020) concluded in their research that there is a need for stronger collaboration between citizens and the scientific community, advocating for scientific communication. Similarly, Shah et al. (2023) highlighted the lack of planned and comprehensive initiatives to strengthen disaster risk communication, emphasizing the need for leaders and policymakers to create a detailed plan to enhance risk communication.

Other primary skills expected from citizens during disasters include moving to safe zones, trusting and collaborating with experts, and minimizing damage. On the other hand, highlighted practical skills among secondary skills include going to assembly areas, moving to higher points, first aid knowledge, calling for help, and information communication to prevent dangerous situations. These skills are critical for disaster management and community resilience. Despite the positive attitude of the community towards assisting emergency personnel in the face of disasters, Elkady et al. (2022) suggest that volunteers may sometimes have the potential to cause harm rather than benefit. Spontaneous volunteers may be at risk of harming themselves and others since they may not have the expertise and skills required to cope with a crisis. Therefore, imparting the identified basic skills to citizens is crucial in this regard.

After a disaster, primary skills expected from citizens by firefighters include assisting search and rescue teams, going to assembly areas and being prepared to wait, healthy communication and coordination, remaining calm, and being hopeful, and collaborating with search and rescue teams. These skills are crucial for providing effective assistance to disaster victims, maintaining organized coordination within

the community, and strengthening solidarity. The research conducted by Elkady et al. (2022) supports the skills identified in this study, emphasizing the importance of playing a significant role in the recovery phase, sharing reliable information at the disaster site with emergency intervention teams, following the advice of emergency personnel on-site, and being prepared with the necessary information and resources to cope with the crisis. Some barriers to community participation in disaster management are also identified. An example of such a barrier is citizens causing harm to themselves or others through intervention and disrupting intervention efforts. Despite these barriers, emergency organizations are in favor of involving the community in intervention and recovery stages. The identified needs and barriers contribute to the definition of procedures and policies that can enhance citizen participation and thus improve social resilience. Emphasis is placed on the importance of obtaining reliable information from the disaster site as soon as possible and adhering to the recommendations of authorities. Additionally, among the secondary skills highlighted by firefighters, first aid, hygiene and personal care, social and psychological support stand out. These skills aim to equip citizens with competence in crucial areas such as maintaining health conditions after a disaster, providing emotional support, and strengthening community solidarity. According to Sommer and Njå (2011), learning to act appropriately in emergencies is fundamentally a result of skill and knowledge concretization, personal experience, and interpersonal sharing.

In conclusion, the emphasis by firefighters on these skills aims to enable citizens to act more effectively during the disaster management process, strengthen the culture of solidarity, and enhance the overall resilience of the community. Acquiring these diverse skills can contribute to making society more prepared and resilient to disasters. Based on the research findings, fundamental disaster literacy skills that should be present in every citizen during and after a disaster have been identified.

During a Disaster: Core Skills

The research results encompass data obtained from the perspective of firefighters and reflect the prominent elements of primary core skills required during a disaster. According to firefighters, the primary essential skills needed during a disaster are as follows:

1. Remaining Calm
 - Firefighters emphasize the importance of individuals remaining calm during a disaster. This skill stands out as the ability to control thoughts and actions without succumbing to panic.
2. Communication Skills
 - Clear and truthful communication is evaluated critically by participants. Being equipped with up-to-date and accurate information is highlighted as the key to effective communication during the disaster management process.
3. Moving to Safe Zones
 - The strategy of escaping from hazardous areas holds vital importance during disaster situations. Firefighters emphasize the fundamental strategy of moving individuals to safe zones to minimize the consequences of disasters.
4. Trusting and Collaborating with Experts
 - Firefighters highlight the significance of trusting experts and collaborating with them during a disaster. This skill encompasses an understanding of coordinating professional help effectively.
5. Minimizing Damage
 - Participants emphasize individuals' abilities to understand and improve conditions in their surroundings. Strategies for minimizing damage are crucial for effective coping after a disaster.

The prioritized core skills by firefighters focus on enabling individuals and communities to ensure their safety, establish effective communication, utilize professional assistance, and minimize damage during disasters. These skills are of critical importance for disaster management and community resilience.

Based on data obtained from the perspective of firefighters, the secondary core skills required during a disaster are as follows:

1. Assembly Area Navigation Skill

- The ability to navigate to designated assembly areas during disaster situations aims to facilitate the organized gathering of the community and transition to a safe zone. This assists individuals in reaching assistance points safely after a disaster.

2. Skill to Climb to High Points (For Flood Disasters)

- The skill to climb to a high point, especially for flood situations, aims to achieve protection against water inundation. This skill is crucial for individuals to reach safe areas in the face of risky situations.

3. First Aid Knowledge

- Firefighters emphasize the importance of basic first aid knowledge during disasters. First aid knowledge aims to intervene effectively in emergency situations and improve the condition of the injured. This skill aims to provide effective assistance and save lives during a disaster.

4. Calling for Help and Information Communication Skill

- The skill of calling out to and communicating information to individuals in one's vicinity signifies the ability to assist others and communicate information. This skill strengthens communication among people in the community, supporting a culture of mutual assistance and solidarity.

5. Hazard Prevention Skill (For Gas Leaks)

- A skill focused on preventing dangerous situations, such as gas leaks, is included among the necessary secondary skills during a disaster. This skill aims to encourage a conscious and proactive response to environmental hazards.

The secondary skills highlighted by firefighters during a disaster aim to address specific and distinct needs, providing practical measures for disaster management and focusing on specific competencies required after a disaster.

After a Disaster: Core Skills

Valuable information is provided about the primary core skills expected from citizens after a disaster, based on the assessments of firefighters. The results derived from firefighters' evaluations regarding primary core skills after a disaster are outlined below:

1. Search and Rescue Assistance Skill

- Firefighters prioritize the skill of assisting search and rescue teams as a primary skill expected from citizens after a disaster. This skill involves providing support to professional teams and identifying those in need of assistance during emergencies. Active contributions of citizens with this skill can help alleviate the consequences of a disaster.

2. Skill to Go to Assembly Areas and Wait

- The skill of going to designated assembly areas and waiting there aims to establish safe organization after a disaster. This skill prevents individuals from moving in an uncontrolled manner, allowing for more effective coordination of assistance.

3. Healthy Communication and Coordination Skill

- Firefighters emphasize the importance of healthy communication and coordination skills among citizens after a disaster. This skill involves effective communication among disaster victims and with professional assistance teams. Accurate and clear communication is crucial for the planning and implementation of effective assistance.

4. Remaining Calm and Hopeful Skill

- Citizens are expected to possess the skill of remaining calm and hopeful after a disaster. This skill represents emotional resilience and a positive attitude during crisis situations. Fostering these qualities can contribute to more effective disaster coping by maintaining high morale within the community.

5. Collaboration Skill with Search and Rescue Teams

- Firefighters highlight the collaboration skill with search and rescue teams as a primary expectation from citizens. This skill involves coordinated actions with professional teams and the capacity for mutual assistance. Collaboration is mentioned as a significant element for more effective and organized disaster assistance.

The research provides a clear perspective from firefighters on the primary core skills expected from citizens after a disaster. These skills serve as a significant guide for ensuring community preparedness for disasters and effective coping strategies.

Important information regarding the secondary core skills expected from citizens after a disaster is also provided based on the assessments of firefighters. The evaluations by firefighters are as follows:

1. First Aid Skill

- Firefighters expect citizens to possess first aid skills after a disaster. This skill, emphasized by two individuals, represents the ability to effectively intervene in health issues at the disaster site. This highlights the importance placed on addressing emergency situations that may arise after a disaster.

2. Hygiene and Personal Care Skill

- The hygiene and personal care skill is mentioned by two individuals. This skill includes measures such as maintaining health conditions, cleanliness, and personal hygiene after a disaster. It signifies the importance of preserving community and individual health.

3. Social and Psychological Support Skill

- The social and psychological support skill represents the ability to provide emotional support to disaster victims and promote solidarity within the community. This skill is emphasized by two individuals, indicating a focus on strengthening community spirit and interpersonal support.

4. Other Secondary Skills

- Other secondary skills are emphasized by only one person each. These skills include the use of social media, accurate information transmission, attention during rescue operations, providing support to disaster victims, silence (for earthquake disasters), social security measures, setting up toilet tents, following instructions from authorities and experts, applying knowledge learned from training, assisting in transportation, and reapplying first aid skills. This diversity reflects the focus of firefighters on addressing various needs within the community and a wide range of skills.

The research highlights the diversity of secondary skills expected by firefighters, reflecting their focus on addressing various needs within the community for enhanced solidarity and safety.

Conclusion

Based on data from the perspective of firefighters, this research highlights the key skills expected from citizens and the importance of these skills. The research identifies various skills that citizens should possess during and after disasters. According to firefighters, key skills that citizens should possess during disasters include staying calm, effective communication, moving to safe areas, trust and cooperation with experts, and damage minimization strategies. The research also highlights search and rescue assistance, going to designated assembly areas and waiting, good communication and coordination, the ability to remain calm and hopeful, and the ability to cooperate with search and rescue teams as key skills expected from citizens after a disaster. Firefighters also focus on secondary skills that citizens need to have a disaster, including first aid, hygiene and personal care, social and psychological support. The research

emphasizes that citizens' possession of this wide range of skills can contribute to making society more prepared and resilient to disasters.

Recommendations

Based on the research findings, the following recommendations have been identified:

1. Educational programs for citizens should be developed based on the core skills emphasized by firefighters before and during disasters. These programs should particularly focus on skills such as remaining calm, communication, moving to safe zones, trusting experts and collaboration, and minimizing damage.
2. Strategies to increase community solidarity should be devised. Skills such as going to assembly areas and climbing to high points should be strengthened through methods that support coordination and mutual assistance within the community.
3. Psychosocial support programs should be established, concentrating on the skills expected after a disaster. These programs should include training on increasing emotional resilience, maintaining a hopeful attitude, and providing support to others.
4. Training programs emphasizing first aid skills should be developed. This can enhance individuals' capacity to effectively intervene in injuries that may occur after a disaster.
5. Training sessions focusing on improving communication and information sharing skills, as highlighted by firefighters, should be organized. This can facilitate efficient information exchange within the community and ensure access to accurate information.
6. Guidance services focusing on the skills expected from citizens after a disaster should be emphasized. These services can support individuals in areas such as assisting search and rescue teams, healthy communication and coordination, remaining calm, and collaborating with professional teams.
7. Training programs should be developed with a focus on modern communication tools, such as social media, as indicated by firefighters. These programs can expedite information exchange within the community and support effective communication.
8. Policies and procedures should be developed to overcome barriers identified in community participation in disaster management. Efforts should concentrate on more effectively involving the community in disaster processes.
9. A mechanism should be established to regularly receive feedback based on information obtained from firefighters' perspectives. This collaboration can lead to the creation of more effective strategies for disaster management.

Further Research

Building on the results of this research, future studies can consider the following recommendations:

1. Research should be conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of disaster management curricula for citizens based on the core skills identified by firefighters. Feedback should be collected to assess and improve the effectiveness of these programs.
2. Further research is needed to more thoroughly examine barriers to community participation in disaster management. Identifying barriers can assist in developing policies and procedures to more effectively involve the community in disaster processes.
3. Research should be conducted to understand the role of communication technologies, social media, and other digital tools in disaster management processes. Strategies should be developed to determine how these technologies can be used effectively.

4. More specific research is needed to enhance psychosocial support and community solidarity after disasters. Strategies can be developed to focus on increasing individual emotional resilience, strengthening community cohesion, and enhancing coping capacities.
5. Research should explore how disaster preparedness and coping skills are affected in different cultures. Understanding how different cultures respond to skills, education, and disaster management strategies can contribute to the development of more effective and culturally sensitive approaches.
6. Disaster management strategies should particularly target vulnerable groups such as children and the elderly. Developing special training programs and strategies for these groups can contribute to overall community resilience.
7. Further research should delve into post-disaster support mechanisms focusing on the secondary skills highlighted by firefighters. This can provide an opportunity to understand how citizens adapt to expected skills after a disaster and how these skills are supported at the community level.

Based on these recommendations, future research in the field of disaster management may need to focus more extensively on developing comprehensive, effective, and community-oriented strategies.

Ethical Approval and Permission

This research was conducted under the research permit E-48995525-622.03-1690224 issued by the İzmir Metropolitan Municipality Fire Department on December 8, 2023. The relevant document has been signed with a secure electronic signature, and the document verification code is identified as "BSCU28JEY4," with the pin code "47762." The aim of the study was to gather insights and recommendations from the İzmir Fire Department Search and Rescue Team. Data collection took place through meetings addressing the question, "What skills should a citizen possess during and after a disaster?" This permission and approval indicate that the research was conducted in accordance with ethical standards and is endorsed by the İzmir Fire Department.

Conflict of interests

No conflict of interest.

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